

TRANSPARENCY OF PUBLIC AUTHORITY AND ADMINISTRATIVE BODIES AND ISSUES OF INFORMATION POLICY

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***Abstract.** Since the main tasks of the information service are to develop the organization's relations with the public, special attention is paid to the issues of ensuring public and parliamentary control over the activities of the state authorities and management bodies of the mass media, establishing strong communication between the authorities and the public. In this scientific article, the legal and theoretical foundations of the state information policy and, accordingly, the information policy of organizations in Uzbekistan were considered. According to the legislation of Uzbekistan, it was studied what practical work is being done to ensure the open and transparent activity of public administration sectors, to establish an effective dialogue with the public. In addition, some outstanding issues were referred for open discussion.*

***Key words:** information policy, privacy, public relations, state bodies, information service, information transparency.*

Introduction. Global information infrastructure can be defined as a continuous network of interactive communications deployed worldwide to provide the infrastructure for new services and activities based on the strategic use of all types of information.

The positive and negative aspects of globalization processes are known to everyone. The problems caused by globalization cover all aspects of human life and

activity. The great socio-political changes that took place at the end of the 20th century, the disruption of the relative balance as a result of the end of the bipolar world, fundamentally changed the ideological landscape of the world. The 20th century was a period of sharp and complex ideological confrontations in the world. At the end of the 20th century, as a result of the end of the bipolar world and the violation of the relative balance, the world's ideological landscape changed radically. In such a situation, recognizing that it is an important task to conduct an effective information policy in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to look for different ways of its implementation and choose the most optimal way. Therefore, researching the experience of developed countries helps to increase the efficiency of the work. The objects of the state information policy are published mass media - newspaper, magazine and book publication, electronic mass media - television, radio, internet, as well as means of communication - telephone, pagers. "Information policy can be considered as a tool of political influence and a means of achieving political goals: the subjects of information policy can use information to influence people's minds, psyche, their morals and their activities within the framework of the interests of the state and civil society and personal interests"[1]. The information space in developed countries and the processes taking place in it depend on the activities of state authorities. In these countries, public administration bodies are widely using the Internet, mobile communication, television and audiovisual systems, as well as traditional printed publications, to maintain the priority position in the information space. At the same time, this shows that it is an effective means of protecting national interests in the context of globalization. At the same time, the provision of information security in society is of great importance in increasing the level of political knowledge of society members and in forming immunity against harmful ideas.

Theoretical basis. A civil society is a democratically organized, free society with transparency and openness. In this society, social evaluation of political and legal events, consideration of public opinion will have a priority position.

The effectiveness of the use of mass media and digital technologies in the provision of openness and transparency of the activities of state authorities and administrative bodies, and the delivery of information can be seen in the following cases:[2]

- firstly, increased confidence in the state administration;
- secondly, the development of legal awareness of citizens;
- thirdly, it is possible to organize effective communication by establishing a dialogue between management bodies and the people;
- fourthly, through communication with the public, it is possible to improve the process of developing laws and ensuring their actual implementation in order to eliminate the problems of the people. “An important task of the information service of the state authorities and management bodies is to explain the extent to which the activities of state organizations, the activities of the adopted normative documents, the adopted normative documents, the implemented plans and programs affect the lives of citizens. The use of PR in government activities improves the relationship between the government and the people. It allows the positive adoption of laws by citizens and their correct implementation in practice”[3]. Indeed, especially in the last two years, when the pandemic and restrictions reigned all over the world, the press secretaries of the organizations tried to answer the questions of the public about the industry in the daily briefings, to provide the public with information and to provide services. The activity of the press secretary, equivalent to the position of the information policy adviser of the head of the organization, must be the fastest, first and most authentic source of news about the organization.

Results. Specialists have a great role in the effective organization of information services of state bodies in the regions. The following are the state units allocated by regional governments for information services[4]:

Andijan region - 5 state units

Samarkand region - 6 state units

Navoi region - 2 state units

Tashkent city - 3 state units

It can be concluded from these numbers that the PR activity of state bodies is not fully regulated and is not provided with sufficient material infrastructure. Under the control of the Information and Mass Communications Agency, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city governments have allocated at least 4 state units in the regional departments of information services, state bodies and organizations[5].

As mentioned above, today the issue of attracting qualified personnel to the field of effective operation of information services of local government bodies has not been resolved at the required level. Information services are not organized in the regional offices of some state bodies and organizations. This means widely promoting the results of the reforms implemented in our country in the regions, regularly informing the population about the issues related to the activities of state bodies and organizations, and on this basis, ensuring full openness and transparency of the activities of state authorities and management bodies.

Discussion. Until now, the issues of conducting the information policy of state bodies and government organizations, ensuring the priority of the principles of openness and transparency in their activities, and cooperation with the mass media in this regard have been studied by many scholars and researchers.

Today, when the issues of positively shaping the image of Uzbekistan and strengthening its promotion in the international media space are very relevant, the practical efforts to effectively organize the information service of state administration and government organizations were analyzed.

As one of the main components that shape the image of the country, the opinion and mood of the people, as well as the openness and transparency of the state administration, the material and technical base of the establishment of the information service of the government organizations, the requirements for the employees and the opportunities created the need to overcome the existing shortcomings by evaluating the performance indicators is still relevant. In addition, the information policy of the

organization carefully considers the issue of privacy of personal data of the audience, the development of the concept of privacy of personal data of service users or applicants through social networks will increase trust in the organization.

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